

A New Utility Evaluation Framework for Data Anonymization in the Context of Mobility

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Abstract

Sharing urban mobility and public transportation data is critical to use the mobility infrastructure of cities to its fullest potential. For data protection reasons, however, the disclosure of data to the public is restricted and only permitted if the anonymity of each individual associated with the dataset can be guaranteed. To achieve anonymity in a given dataset, numerous approaches can be applied, while each approach follows a different definition of anonymity. One of the most used definitions is k -anonymity, which builds on the building of equivalence classes so that each row in a dataset belongs to an equivalence class that contains at least k rows that cannot be distinguished. Naturally, this can be achieved by multiple realizations. However, the question is which realization will provide the highest utility for future real-world applications. Currently, abstract metrics are used to assess the utility of different k -anonymizations, based on the structure of the dataset. However, these abstract metrics do not properly reflect the usefulness of the anonymized datasets in real-world applications. Hence, in this work, we provide a novel framework that helps to evaluate the given abstract metrics from the literature in terms of their performance in measuring utility in the context of urban mobility. To do this, we define a set of potential data science use cases that can be derived from a publicly available dataset on taxi drives and compute multiple realizations of k -anonymity. By training prediction models on the original dataset and the anonymized datasets and comparing the corresponding performance decrease with the abstract metrics from the literature, we are able to derive recommendations on the usage of abstract metrics to evaluate the utility of potential realizations to achieve k -anonymity.

Keywords: Utility, k -anonymity, evaluation, machine learning, mobility

1 Introduction

In recent years, the availability of data has significantly accelerated the technical progress. However, in many cases, data is often directly related to the personal information of individuals, which raises several privacy concerns when shared indiscriminately [1]. Therefore, various approaches to anonymize data were developed, such as k -anonymity [2]–[6], differential-privacy [7]–[9], l -diversity [10], [11], t -closeness [12], [13] and many more.

For all of these anonymization approaches, there are multiple metrics that try to estimate the utility of the resulting anonymized datasets, e.g. see [1], [14], [15]. However, most of the utility metrics available in the literature are purely abstract since they only rely on the changes in data structure compared to the original data. These metrics inherently neglect the utility of an anonymized dataset in real-world applications.

From a data owner perspective, the question arises as to which of these abstract metrics should be used as an objective in the anonymization process to provide anonymized data with high utility for a wide range of applications. To the best of our knowledge, this question has not been addressed in the literature so far.

Hence, with this work, we make the following contribution:

- We identified a research gap that most metrics for evaluating anonymized data only refer to the structure of the dataset and not to the utility in real-world applications.
- To close this research gap, we propose a general framework that enables us to assess the applicability of abstract metrics to measure the utility of an anonymized dataset in real-world applications. The resulting knowledge helps data owners to choose the right abstract metric for the data anonymization process to offer high-utility anonymized datasets for a wide range of applications.
- We evaluate our framework using a publicly available dataset in the context of urban mobility.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows.

In Section 2, we give an overview of existing approaches for data anonymization and abstract metrics from the literature, followed by the introduction of our utility evaluation framework in Section 3. The results of our extensive computational study are presented and discussed in Section 4. Section 5 concludes our work and gives an outlook on future research directions.

2 Fundamentals and Related Work

In this section, we give a brief overview of approaches to anonymizing data and address the concepts of k -anonymity in more detail. Further, we introduce the notation used in this work and present the abstract evaluation metrics from the literature.

2.1 Data Anonymization

Data anonymization is a well-studied subject in research and offers many privacy models and solution approaches that prevent any privacy-related information from being disclosed (see [2], [15], [16]). According to [1] these models can be mostly grouped into:

- privacy models to prevent record linkage such as k -anonymity [2]–[6],
- privacy models to prevent attribute and table linkage such as l -diversity [10], [11] and t -closeness [12], [13],
- differential privacy models [7]–[9] to prevent skewness and similarity attacks.

Moreover, all attributes, i.e. the different columns of a dataset, can be classified into four categories. These categories play an important role in the anonymization process. A quasi-identifying attribute (QI) means that the information can be used in combination with another dataset to assign sensitive information to a specific person. Sensitive information is only intended for oneself and should not be publicly available. Identifying attributes contain the information to assign sensitive information directly to a specific person. It follows that identifying attributes must be removed to ensure anonymity. Furthermore, there are non-sensitive attributes, which are neither quasi-identifying nor sensitive or identifying.

All quasi-identifying attributes of a dataset must be specially considered in the anonymization process so that the data cannot later be used to identify specific persons. One possible way is to generalize the data of the quasi-identifying attributes, as with k -anonymity to ensure privacy protection.

All privacy models have in common that they modify the original data of the quasi-identifying attributes of a dataset to prevent privacy-related information from being disclosed. These modifications can be classified in five potential types (see [1]):

- **Generalization:** During generalization, all values of quasi-identifying attributes are replaced with an abstraction of the original value. There are two main categories. Global recording replaces all values with a more generic value. This means that if, e.g. a value $v1$ is replaced by V , all values of $v1$ in the same column must be replaced by V .

In contrast, local recording allows more flexibility, e.g. if a value $v1$ is replaced by $V1$, another occurrence of the value $v1$ in the same column can be replaced by $V2$.

- **Suppression:** During suppression, certain values or tuples of values can be suppressed or deleted from the dataset.
- **Bucketisation:** Bucketization breaks the association between quasi-identifiers and sensitive attributes by splitting them into different datasets. Using a common attribute, e.g. "group-id", each sensitive attribute value can then be assigned to a group of individuals from the other dataset.
- **Permutation:** Permutation separates a quasi-identifying attribute and a numeric sensitive attribute by dividing the dataset into groups and then shuffling the sensitive attribute values inside each group.
- **Perturbation:** Perturbation changes the data so that they no longer correspond to the original value, for example by adding noise. With this method, the distortion of the statistical information values remains low, while a synthetic dataset replaces the original data.

2.2 k -Anonymity

In this section, we introduce k -anonymity as an anonymity definition since it is well suited for tabular data in the context of mobility (see [16], [17]), such as the dataset used in our computational study in Section 4. Therefore, this section addresses the concepts and methods to achieve k -anonymity in more detail.

The k -anonymity approach aims to assign values of quasi-identifying attributes to groups or intervals to prevent the disclosure of personal information. With this approach, it is very unlikely that an attacker combining data from different datasets will be able to retrieve personal information. This also holds for datasets that are potentially published in the future and currently unknown [2].

Definition k -anonymity [2]:

A dataset \mathcal{D}_i with the quasi-identifiers $QI_{\mathcal{D}_i}$ satisfies the k -anonymity property if and only if each sequence of values of a row in $\mathcal{D}_i [QI_{\mathcal{D}_i}]$ appears with at least k occurrences in $\mathcal{D}_i [QI_{\mathcal{D}_i}]$.

This means the values of quasi-identifying attributes must be generalized until each row in the dataset cannot be distinguished in the quasi-identifying attributes from a set of at least k different rows.

2.3 k -Anonymity, Generalization and Suppression

This section describes the interaction of k -anonymity, generalization, and suppression.

In general, there are two options to achieve a certain degree of k -anonymity when anonymizing a dataset.

The first option is to set the generalization level of the quasi-identifying attributes, i.e. the interval sizes for the generalization. It is important to ensure that all values of the quasi-identifying attributes can be assigned to the resulting intervals in such a way that at least k rows of the dataset can no longer differ in their quasi-identifying attributes, i.e. the k -anonymity property holds.

The second option is to introduce a suppression limit to achieve a lower level of generalization, i.e. smaller intervals, in order to lose less information. This suppression limit allows to suppress a maximum of p percent of the data in the dataset. This means that the rows that cannot be sorted into the generalization intervals to satisfy the k -anonymity property can be suppressed. However, depending on the suppression limit, only a maximum number of rows can be suppressed.

If the k -anonymity property is still not achieved, either the suppression limit can be set to a higher value, or the generalization level and the associated interval sizes can be increased until the k -anonymity property is satisfied.

Overall, k -anonymity is a trade-off between the loss of data through suppression, the loss of data accuracy by increasing generalization intervals, and the loss of privacy protection by reducing k . Thus, finding a good way to evaluate anonymization regarding real-world utilities is even more important, as there are so many possible variations.

2.4 Notation

To increase the robustness of our study, we propose to consider multiple real-world use cases $i \in \{1, \dots, I\}$. For these use cases, we define the set of original datasets $\mathcal{D} = \{\mathcal{D}_1, \dots, \mathcal{D}_I\}$, where each dataset $\mathcal{D}_i \in \mathcal{D}$ is related to the unique use case i . For each dataset \mathcal{D}_i , we further consider J multiple anonymizations $\mathcal{D}_i^A = \{\mathcal{D}_i^{(1)}, \dots, \mathcal{D}_i^{(J)}\}$. This means $\mathcal{D}_i^{(1)}$ is the first possible anonymization while $\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}$ is the j -th possible anonymization of dataset \mathcal{D}_i , with $j = 1, \dots, J$.

Next, we make use of a set with M different abstract metrics $U_A = \{U_A^1, \dots, U_A^M\}$ which represent, e.g. approaches from [1] but are not restricted to those. In this work, we restrict each abstract metric $U_A^m \in U_A$ with $m = 1, \dots, M$ to values from the interval $[0, 1]$.

The notations corresponding to the real-world utility for a given use case i are analogous to the notations of the abstract metrics. We define a set of I real-world metrics $U_R = \{U_R^1, \dots, U_R^I\}$. Each of these real-world metrics is tailored

to a particular use case i , which could represent generating a prediction model from the dataset \mathcal{D}_i . Further, we define scalar functions based on these real-world metrics $u_{U_i^R}(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathcal{D}_i^{(j)})$ that map a dataset \mathcal{D}_i associated with the i -th use case and its j -th anonymization to the corresponding real-world utility value within the interval $[0, 1]$.

2.5 Abstract Metrics

The following section introduces a subset of abstract metrics from the literature that is used in our work.

Among the conducted selection, we aim to identify those abstract metrics that can measure the utility of an anonymized dataset concerning real-world use cases most precisely. The knowledge of this best-performing abstract metric would enable data owners to anonymize their data according to this metric in such a way that the data are highly useful for various potential applications.

2.5.1 Minimum-Distortion Metric

The first metric introduced in this work is the minimum-distortion metric (MD), which is discussed, e.g. in [1]. The MD metric penalizes any value in an anonymized dataset that has been generalized compared to the original dataset. For this work, the following equation is used to calculate the MD-value:

$$\mathcal{MD} = 1 - \left[\frac{1}{|\mathcal{D}_i|} \left(n \cdot \frac{\sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \frac{g(c)}{g_{max}(c)}}{|\mathcal{C}|} + u \right) \right] \in [0, 1] \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), $|\mathcal{D}_i|$ denotes the number of rows in the dataset, n the number of not suppressed rows in the anonymized dataset, and u the number of suppressed rows, with $|\mathcal{D}_i| = n + u$. Furthermore, $\mathcal{C} = \{c_1, \dots, c_q\}$ denotes the set of anonymized columns in the anonymized dataset. These refer to the quasi-identifying attributes in the dataset. The function $g : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ denotes the generalization level and $g_{max}(c)$ the theoretically maximum possible generalization level during the anonymization of column $c \in \mathcal{C}$.

The abstract utility value depends on the number of generalization levels set in the anonymization process. To avoid this disadvantage of Equation (1), we modify the basic version of the MD metric as given in Equation (2).

$$\mathcal{MD}_v = 1 - \left[\frac{1}{|\mathcal{D}_i|} \left(n \cdot \frac{\sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \frac{v_g(c)}{v_{g_{max}}(c)}}{|\mathcal{C}|} + u \right) \right] \in [0, 1] \quad (2)$$

Here, $v_g(c)$ denotes the interval size of the generalized column c and $v_{g_{max}}(c)$ describes the theoretical interval size of column $c \in \mathcal{C}$ at the maximum

generalization level for a given dataset.

When we refer to the minimum distortion values metric (MDv) in our work, we mean the MD calculated according to Equation (2), otherwise only MD means the calculation according to Equation (1).

For Equation (1) and (2) holds: If all data in the anonymized dataset are suppressed, which corresponds to $n = 0$ and $u = |\mathcal{D}_i|$, this results in $\mathcal{MD} = \mathcal{MD}_v = 0$. This behavior is associated with a complete lack of utility. If the investigated dataset is original and unmodified, i.e. $n = |\mathcal{D}_i|$ and $u = 0$, no suppression is applied, and no anonymization is conducted, which corresponds to a generalization level $g(c) = v_g(c) = 0$ for each column c , then the abstract utility values results in $\mathcal{MD} = \mathcal{MD}_v = 1$ for Equations (1) and (2). This is associated with a maximum utility as it represents the utility of the original dataset.

2.5.2 Discernibility Metric

The next abstract metric used in this work is the discernibility metric (DM), which has been introduced e.g. in [10], [15]. This metric attempts to maintain the discernibility between tuples in the anonymized dataset as much as possible without violating the properties of the k -anonymization. A penalty is assigned to each tuple of the anonymized dataset based on how many tuples are not distinguishable from this tuple. This can be mathematically realized as follows, according to [15]:

$$\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{DM}}(h, k) = \sum_{\forall \mathcal{E}_l \in \Omega \text{ s.t. } |\mathcal{E}_l| \geq k} |\mathcal{E}_l|^2 + \sum_{\forall \mathcal{E}_l \in \Omega \text{ s.t. } |\mathcal{E}_l| < k} |\mathcal{D}_i| |\mathcal{E}_l| \quad (3)$$

In Equation (3), $h : \mathcal{D}_i \rightarrow \mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}$ denotes a function that anonymizes the origin dataset \mathcal{D}_i to the anonymized dataset $\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}$. Through this function h , we get the set of equivalence classes $\Omega = \{\mathcal{E}_1, \dots, \mathcal{E}_L\}$. Here, we define an equivalence class \mathcal{E}_l with $l = 1, \dots, L$ as follows:

$$\mathcal{E}_l := \left\{ r, r_s \in \mathcal{D}_i^{(j)} : r [QI_{\mathcal{D}_i}] = r_s [QI_{\mathcal{D}_i}] \wedge r \neq r_s \wedge r_s \notin \mathcal{E}_{1, \dots, L \setminus \{l\}}, \right. \\ \left. s = 1, \dots, |\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}|, s \in \mathbb{N} \right\} \quad (4)$$

Here, r and r_s denote two different rows of the anonymized dataset $\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}$. The notation in Equation (4) means that each equivalence class contains a subset of rows from the anonymized dataset, with the property that each row is not distinguishable in its quasi-identifying attributes from any other row in the same equivalence class. Furthermore, the degree of the anonymization is denoted as k according to the k -anonymity model. In this equation, the power of two of the cardinality of all equivalence classes $\mathcal{E}_l \in \Omega$ that satisfy the k -property is summed up, and the cardinality of all equivalence classes

that don't satisfy the k -property is multiplied by the total number of rows from the dataset $|\mathcal{D}_i|$ and summed up. It is equivalent that the number of suppressed values u is multiplied by the total number of rows in the dataset $|\mathcal{D}_i|$ for the second sum in Equation (3).

The following Equation (5) normalizes Equation (3) in the range $[0, 1]$:

$$\mathcal{DM}(h, k) = 1 - \left[\frac{\sum_{\forall \mathcal{E}_l \in \Omega \text{ s.t. } |\mathcal{E}_l| \geq k} |\mathcal{E}_l|^2 + \sum_{\forall \mathcal{E}_l \in \Omega \text{ s.t. } |\mathcal{E}_l| < k} |\mathcal{D}_i| |\mathcal{E}_l|}{|\mathcal{D}_i|^2} + \frac{k \cdot (u - |\mathcal{D}_i|)}{|\mathcal{D}_i|^2} \right] \quad (5)$$

First, it can be recognized that the term of Equation (3) is divided by $|\mathcal{D}_i|^2$, since the maximum value of the upper term can be $|\mathcal{D}_i|^2$ in the case all values of the anonymized dataset are suppressed. Furthermore, the term $+\frac{k \cdot (u - |\mathcal{D}_i|)}{|\mathcal{D}_i|^2}$ is added to get a value of one for the case when a dataset is not anonymized, which means the full information of the dataset is available. For this case, it follows $k = 1$, no suppressed values ($u = 0$), and all equivalence classes $\mathcal{E}_l \in \Omega$ include only one element ($|\mathcal{E}_l| = 1 \forall l = 1, \dots, L$). Because of this, the result of Equation (5) is one.

Another case is when the dataset is k -anonymized, no data is suppressed, $u = 0$, and all equivalence classes $\mathcal{E}_l \in \Omega$ include k elements ($|\mathcal{E}_l| = k \forall l = 1, \dots, L$). This means that the anonymization provides the best possible amount of information without violating the k -anonymity property. In this case, too, the value of the DM is one.

If all data points of the anonymized dataset are suppressed, $u = |\mathcal{D}_i|$, we don't have information for learning, and the value of DM is zero.

2.5.3 Ambiguity Metric

The third abstract metric, the ambiguity metric (AM), is presented as introduced in [18]. This metric also considers the generalization of anonymized attributes. For example, how large is the emerging interval.

$$\mathcal{AM}(\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}) = \frac{\sum_{r=1}^{|\mathcal{D}_i|} \prod_{c=1}^n f(\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}[r][c])}{|\mathcal{D}_i|} \quad (6)$$

In Equation (6), $f : \mathcal{D}_i^{(j)} \times \dots \times \mathcal{D}_i^{(j)} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ denotes a function, which assigns a value to a data cell for the anonymized dataset.

In the case of categorical data, the function returns the number of distinct values of a group in the data cell. In the case of continuous data, the function returns the interval size of the interval in the data cell plus one, according to [18].

The AM multiplies all function values from the attributes of one row and sums these values up across all rows.

$$\overline{\mathcal{AM}}(\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}) = 1 - \left[\frac{\sum_{r=1}^{|\mathcal{D}_i|} \prod_{c=1}^n \frac{f(\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}[r][c]) - 1}{\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}[c][r]) - 1}}{|\mathcal{D}_i|} \right] \in [0, 1] \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) normalizes Equation (6) to the interval $[0, 1]$. To achieve this, the function $\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{D}_i^{(j)} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ returns the same as function f , but for the theoretically maximum possible generalization level.

The AM does not consider the suppressed values in the anonymized dataset, the AM only considers the data to which they can be applied according to the definition.

3 Utility Evaluation Framework

The goal of our utility evaluation framework presented in this work is to assess the ability to estimate the utility of datasets in terms of real-world applications.

With such an evaluation, we are able to identify generally applicable abstract metrics that can measure the utility of datasets with high quality. Our field of interest in this work is the data utility value in the mobility domain, but the framework is easily extendable for other use cases and data domains. The idea to determine a generally valid data utility value definition with this framework is to investigate the correlation between the utility values achieved by specific abstract metrics, presented in Section 2.5 and the realized utility values, presented in Section 3.1.

In the following, we present how to compute the utility in real-world use cases based on an original and the associated anonymized dataset. Next, we map these so-called, real-world utility values with the associated abstract metric values presented in Section 2.5. Since our framework proposes to conduct this mapping for multiple different use cases, we can derive the correlations of these abstract metrics with the real-world utilities.

3.1 Realworld Utility Metrics

In the following, we introduce metrics to measure the utility of anonymized datasets in real-world applications. These metrics are henceforth denoted as real-world metrics. In this work, we concentrate on the utility of data to train prediction models with approaches from machine learning. One kind of possible prediction models are regressions.

One of the most popular metrics for evaluating the performance of a regression model is the Mean-Absolute-Error (MAE) [19]:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{N} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^N |\hat{y}_i - y_i| \quad (8)$$

We can use the MAE to compare the performance of the models. In Equation (8), \hat{y}_i denotes the prediction of the label y_i from the test dataset using the corresponding model.

Another popular metric for evaluating the performance of regression models is the Mean-Absolute-Percentage-Error (MAPE) [20]:

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{N} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^N \left(\frac{|\hat{y}_i - y_i|}{y_i} \right) \quad (9)$$

The MAPE is also well adapted for forecasting models, see [20].

Without loss of generality, we define a function $\mu \in \{\text{MAE}, \text{MAPE}\}$, which measures the performance of regression models, with $\mu : Y \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, where Y denotes the set of all possible predictions of the model.

For comparison, we train one model $\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i}$ with the original dataset \mathcal{D}_i and another model $\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}}$ with the anonymized dataset $\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}$. To measure the utility loss between $\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i}$ to $\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}}$, we evaluate both models with the same test dataset. Then, we determine the real-world utility of different anonymizations compared to the original dataset in real-world applications as specified in Equation (10):

$$u_{U_R^i}^\mu(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}) = \frac{\mu(\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i})}{\mu(\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}})} \in [0, 1] \quad (10)$$

This allows us to specify and scale the real-world utility as a real-world metric $u_{U_R^i}^\mu(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathcal{D}_i^{(j)})$. Here, U_R^i stands for the real-world utility of use case i with R as the symbol for real-world and not abstract. Further, u^μ stands for the scalar utility comparison function of the real-world utilities U_R^i between the original dataset \mathcal{D}_i and the anonymized dataset $\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}$ with μ as the performance measure of the models.

In Equations (8) - (10), we assume that a regression model for a specific prediction use case has been trained until convergence for the original dataset \mathcal{D}_i and the anonymized dataset $\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}$ such that the performance measure μ can be determined for both datasets.

If $\mu(\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i})$ and $\mu(\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}})$ are equal, this means we don't have a real-world utility loss with the applied anonymization for the specific use case i . It follows the real-world utility value $u_{U_R^i}^\mu(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathcal{D}_i^{(j)})$ is one.

Figure 1: Computation procedure to get the real-world utility.

If $\mu(\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}})$ is larger than $\mu(\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i})$ then there is a real-world utility loss in the anonymized dataset $\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}$. For $\mu(\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}}) \gg \mu(\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i})$ the real-world utility of the anonymized dataset tends towards zero.

Figure 1 visualizes the process to determine the real-world utility $u_{UR}^\mu(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathcal{D}_i^{(j)})$. As illustrated, the data are divided into a training and test dataset. The first model $\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i}$ is trained with the original training dataset \mathcal{D}_i , and the second model $\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}}$ is trained with the anonymized training dataset $\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}$. Next, our framework evaluates the performance of each of the models using the identical test dataset and according to the performance measure μ such as MAE or MAPE. In the last step, Equation (10) is used to determine the real-world utility, quantifying the information loss of the anonymized training dataset $\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}$ compared to the original training dataset \mathcal{D}_i in terms of the considered use case i .

3.2 Description of the Framework

With these definitions, we describe the architecture and procedure of our framework to evaluate the ability of abstract metrics to evaluate the real-world utility of anonymized datasets.

We assume there is a set of datasets $\mathcal{D} = \{\mathcal{D}_i \mid i = 1, \dots, I\}$ where each dataset \mathcal{D}_i is associated with a different use case i . Then, all datasets $\mathcal{D}_i \in \mathcal{D}$ can be anonymized that we obtain for each dataset \mathcal{D}_i a set of anonymized Datasets \mathcal{D}_i^A .

Next, it is important to ensure that the abstract metrics U_A match to the

selected anonymization techniques. This means that an abstract metric U_A^m that only evaluates generalization can also only evaluate anonymized datasets that have been anonymized with generalization and not e.g. with noise.

Further, the values of each abstract metric U_A^m are computed for each anonymized dataset $\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}$, and the real-world utility $u_{U_R}^\mu(\mathcal{D}_i, \mathcal{D}_i^{(j)})$ is evaluated compared to the original dataset \mathcal{D}_i using the learned models $\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i}$ and $\mathcal{M}^{\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}}$, for all use cases $i = 1, \dots, I$.

With these results, the correlations between each abstract metric $U_A^m \in U_A$ and the real-world utilities $u_{U_R}^\mu$ for each use case i can be calculated. It follows that each anonymized dataset $\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)} \in \mathcal{D}_i^A$ contributes one data point for the calculation of the correlation.

Finally, the output of the evaluation framework is a correlation table with these correlations. The x-axis of this correlation table contains the different use cases i and the y-axis the abstract metrics U_A .

The big advantage of our evaluation framework is that it is built in a modular architecture. This modular architecture makes it easy to extend the framework if other real-world use cases i should be added to the evaluation. Thereby, another use case i , can also take other data types into account if the anonymization and abstract metrics are configured correctly. In addition, further abstract metrics U_A^m can be considered, and other anonymizations $\mathcal{D}_i^{(j)}$ can be added and evaluated.

Overall, our framework enables the identification of abstract metrics U_A that precisely assess the utility of anonymized datasets in a wide range of real-world applications.

4 Computational Study

Our computational study is based on a publicly available dataset in the context of urban mobility. We use this dataset to evaluate the applicability of abstract metrics for the utility estimation of anonymized datasets in real-world use cases using our framework presented in Section 3.2. The dataset we use to derive the use cases considered in this work is introduced in detail in Section 4.1. To improve the quality of the open-source data, we conduct a data cleaning and preparation process, as described in Section 4.2. Further, we give an overview of the context of the data in Section 4.2. In Section 4.3, we describe the anonymization process and present the properties of the anonymized datasets in tabular form. Next, the used prediction models are described in more detail in Section 4.4. In Section 4.5, we close this chapter by presenting the obtained results of evaluating the correlations between the utility values obtained by abstract metrics and those obtained by use case specific real-world metrics as specified by our framework, see Section 3.1.

4.1 New York Taxi dataset

The New York Taxi dataset [21] is a widely known public mobility dataset [22], [23]. This dataset includes information collected by recording all taxi trips from the yellow and green taxi companies in New York over the last few years. These data were made available to the public with specific dependencies. The dataset contains approximately 200 million taxi trips per year [22]. We make use of the data from the year 2015.

For this work, the most important attributes are given as follows:

- **Pick-up and drop-off date time:** Timestamp when a passenger was picked up and dropped off
- **Trip distance:** Total distance of a taxi drive in miles from the taximeter
- **Pick-up and drop-off location:** Longitude and latitude of the pick-up and drop-off location
- **Pick-up and drop-off zones:** The pick-up and drop-off zones from a passenger
- **Total amount:** Price of the taxi drive including taxes and tips in \$
- **Trip duration:** Actual trip duration given in seconds

We use these attributes to create machine learning use cases to assess our framework.

4.2 Data pre-processing

This section describes the data pre-processing steps. First, we extend the dataset by computing a prediction of the trip distance and duration between the pick-up and drop-off locations based on static traffic information. Our used routing service considers the street network in New York with the maximum speed specifications. However, it does not consider current traffic situations such as traffic jams. The predicted distance between pick-up and drop-off positions is given in meters, and the corresponding duration is given in seconds.

To compute the distance and duration between the different zones resulting from different anonymizations, we use the center of each zone as a coordinate point. The next important step is to remove outliers and irrational data points to achieve a high quality of the learned model at the end. In the first step, we remove data associated with a price higher than 100\$ and less than 0\$ to consider the typical price range for taxi trips in New York. Moreover, all taxi trips must transport at least one passenger to be representative. All

Figure 2: Scatter plots of different dimensions of the New York Taxi dataset including linear regression functions.

data entries violating this constraint are removed as well. Next, the prediction of the trip distance must be between 0 and 30,000 meters, and the prediction of the trip duration must be less than two hours to restrict the dataset to well-represented and similar taxi trips from which patterns can be learned to enable a good prediction quality.

Figures 2 show the correlations between the price and the reality and predicted trip distance and duration. All figures include 1,000,000 data points recorded between June 30 and July 15, 2015, in the state of New York, and show a high correlation between the price and the trip distance or duration. The lateral density plots show that the dataset is still slightly unbalanced because more taxi trips have a lower distance, duration, and price. Figure 2a and 2c show that the predicted and the accurate trip distance from the taximeter have a similar distribution. It follows that we use the predicted trip distance instead of the trip distance of the taximeter to train the model because we only have the predicted distance for taxi trips in the future.

The x-axis labels of Figures 2b and 2d show that the predicted time is less than the time needed in reality, as traffic jams often occur in New York. It follows that it takes much longer to reach the destination than predicted without up-to-date traffic information. The predicted duration is usually

less than half as long, but the price is still correlated.

Furthermore, we also use more data from other time intervals to get more robust results at the end. For simplicity, if we refer to data from February, we mean the last 1,000,000 recorded data points between February 13 and February 15, 2015. The same applies to October, with 1,000,000 recorded taxi trips between September 24 and October 15, 2015.

4.3 Anonymization

This section describes the anonymization process and presents the properties of the anonymized datasets in tabular form at the end. We use an open-source software tool ARX for the anonymization. The tool itself is documented in [24] and builds on several research articles, see e.g. [25]–[27]. In particular, we use the ARX tool to anonymize tabular data using k -anonymity. Among various techniques to achieve k -anonymity provided by ARX, we apply the optimal-based technique described in [28].

We specify that pick-up longitude, pick-up latitude, drop-off longitude, and drop-off latitude are quasi-identifiers of the New York taxi dataset, because knowledge of the exact pick-up and drop-off locations of trips might lead to the disclosure of the individual’s private information. A generalization hierarchy of eight hierarchy levels is created for these quasi-identifying attributes. The first generalization level includes intervals with a length of 0.0045 for latitudes and 0.006 for longitudes, starting from the smallest value. This corresponds to a rectangle zone of approximately 500 x 500 meters in New York, US. Then, for the next generalization level, the zone sizes are quadrupled. That corresponds to a rectangle zone of around 1000 x 1000 meters. The zone size is now always quadrupled from hierarchy level to hierarchy level until all values fit into the same interval. The largest interval at the eighth hierarchy level has a length of about 0.48 or 0.35, depending on the longitude or latitude and the exact selected data.

In our study, we always set the maximum suppression limit for all anonymizations to five percent.

Additionally, we take different values of k to obtain different anonymized datasets with different generalization levels of the quasi-identifying attribute, which corresponds to different-sized pick-up and drop-off zones. For each k , we always select the combination of generalization levels with the lowest sum of all generalization levels.

With this procedure, we obtain a set of anonymized datasets, which are described in the following Table 1. Table 1 shows the different properties of the anonymized datasets. For example, the first anonymized dataset was anonymized with $k=2$, and the generalization levels (1, 2, 1, 2) was applied to the dataset. This means that the pick-up- and drop-off zones in the first anonymization have a size of approximately 500x1000 meters.

In order to obtain a higher validity of the results, we also consider the data

Number:	k	Hierarchy-Level:	Pick-up Zone Size:	Drop-off Zone Size:
1	2	(1, 2, 1, 2)	500x1000 meter	500x1000 meter
2	3	(2, 2, 2, 2)	1000x1000 meter	1000x1000 meter
3	4	(1, 1, 3, 3)	500x500 meter	2000x2000 meter
4	5	(3, 1, 3, 2)	2000x500 meter	2000x1000 meter
5	7	(4, 1, 4, 1)	4000x500 meter	4000x500 meter
6	8	(3, 2, 3, 2)	2000x1000 meter	2000x1000 meter
7	9	(3, 3, 2, 2)	2000x2000 meter	1000x1000 meter
8	10	(1, 2, 4, 3)	500x1000 meter	4000x2000 meter
9	13	(4, 3, 1, 3)	4000x2000 meter	500x2000 meter
10	15	(1, 2, 4, 4)	500x1000 meter	4000x4000 meter
11	20	(3, 3, 3, 3)	2000x2000 meter	2000x2000 meter
12	25	(2, 4, 2, 4)	1000x4000 meter	1000x4000 meter
13	30	(1, 2, 4, 5)	500x1000 meter	4000x8000 meter
14	50	(1, 2, 5, 5)	500x1000 meter	8000x8000 meter
15	70	(3, 3, 4, 4)	2000x2000 meter	4000x4000 meter
16	100	(2, 5, 3, 5)	1000x8000 meter	2000x8000 meter
17	200	(4, 4, 4, 4)	4000x4000 meter	4000x4000 meter
18	300	(3, 4, 4, 5)	2000x4000 meter	4000x8000 meter
19	700	(4, 5, 4, 5)	4000x8000 meter	4000x8000 meter
20	1000	(3, 4, 6, 6)	2000x4000 meter	16000x16000 meter

Table 1: Used anonymization properties for the dataset before July 15, 2015.

from February and October 2015. The exact anonymization properties of the corresponding anonymizations of these original datasets are given in the same tabular structure in the Appendix A.1, see Tables A1 and A2.

4.4 Prediction models

This section describes the prediction models for the real-world use cases of our computational study, see Section 3.1.

We use the histogram-based gradient boosting regression tree from the library scikit-learn as the basic regression model [29]. We chose this tree-based regression model because these regression tree models often perform better than deep-learning approaches with much less computational effort and without having to specify many model hyperparameters and the network architecture [30].

All regression models derived from the basic model regarding a given training dataset are always trained with a maximum of 1000 iterations and a learning rate of 0.05. The objective of the regression models is to minimize the MAE during the training. Note that hyperparameter tuning to improve convergence of the training process is out of the scope of this work.

We implement three use cases, $I = 3$, all with the objective of predicting the price of taxi trips from the presented New York taxi dataset in Section 4.1. Note, that the input parameters for the use cases vary as described as follows:

- **Use Case D :** In the first use case, named D for distance, the regression model takes the computed trip distances between the start- and end-coordinates of the taxi trips as input.
- **Use Case DT :** In the second use case, named DT for distance and times, the regression model receives the computed trip duration between the start- and end-coordinates, the pick-up hour, and the week-day of the taxi trips as input in addition to the computed trip distance from use case D .
- **Use Case DTZ :** In the third use case, named DTZ for distance, times, and zones, the regression model receives the pick-up and drop-off coordinates of the taxi trips as input to consider the different zones, as well as the computed trip distance and the times from use case DT .

Since the pick-up and drop-off locations are represented as spatial rectangles in the anonymized datasets \mathcal{D}_i^A , we consider the center of these areas as input for the training process of our prediction models.

4.5 Results

This section presents the main results of our computational study and answers the initial research question of how abstract metrics perform in evaluating the real-world utility of anonymized datasets. This question is answered based on correlation coefficients between abstract metric values and real-world utility values. A high correlation coefficient indicates a good performance of an abstract metric to evaluate anonymized datasets in terms of the real-world utility of the associated use case. The real-world use cases, which should represent a wide range of real-world applications, were implemented in the form of machine learning models, as presented in Section 4.4.

Figures 3 show the correlations between the abstract metrics and the real-world utilities for the price prediction of the New York taxi dataset from July 2015. Figure 3a shows the correlation coefficients when the real-world utility is evaluated with the MAE, see Equations (8) and (10), and Figure 3b for the evaluation with MAPE, see Equations (9) and (10).

In general, the correlation coefficients of Figures 3 can be interpreted as follows: The correlation coefficient 0.91 in Figure 3a in the first column and the second row, indicates that the abstract MDv values, see Section 2.5.1, of the different anonymizations correlate linearly with 0.91 to the real-world utility values of the different anonymizations of the use case D .

Figure 4 demonstrates how the correlation coefficients between abstract and real-world metrics are derived. For the considered correlation coefficient 0.91, Figure 4a shows that the MDv values of the different anonymizations in combination with the corresponding real-world utility values are close to

(a) Evaluated with the MAE

(b) Evaluated with the MAPE

Figure 3: Correlation coefficients plots between abstract metrics and real-world utility values for July 2015.

(a) Evaluated with the MAE

(b) Evaluated with the MAE

Figure 4: Building of correlation coefficients between a specific abstract metric and a real-world utility for July 2015.

a linear regression line, resulting in a high correlation. Further, Figure 4b shows that the data points of the abstract AM values and the real-world utility values of the use case *DTZ* are a little further away from the regression line, resulting in a lower correlation of 0.8.

In Figure 3b, it can be seen that the correlation coefficients with the MAE are generally slightly higher than with the MAPE, see Figure 3b. We assume that this is the case since the MAE was always minimized as an objective during the training of the regression models, which does not always deliver the same results as the MAPE, which can lead to small differences during the evaluation of the real-world utility values, which can have a negative effect on the correlation coefficients.

In addition, Figures 3 show that the correlation coefficients between each specific abstract metric and all associated different real-world utility values are approximately constant and independent of the use case. This leads us

Figure 5: Correlation plots between abstract metrics and real-world utility values from the New York taxi dataset from February, July, and October 2015.

to the assumption, although not sufficiently shown, that the abstract metrics perform equivalently for different real-world use cases. This means that the performance of the abstract metrics to measure the real-world utility is independent of the specific use case.

Both Figures 3a and 3b show that the MDv, see Equation (2), with the interval size of the generalized attribute values as input has the highest correlation to the real-world utilities for our use cases. This means that it would be best for a data owner to maximize the MDv value during the anonymization process since the probability of obtaining a high real-world utility for a wide range of applications is at the highest. Furthermore, the DM provides a higher correlation than the AM.

Next, Figures 5 show the correlation coefficients tables resulting from the calculations with even more data, using the February and October data subsets in addition to the July dataset.

The individual correlation figures for February and October are in the Appendix A.2, see Figures A1 and A2. Here, we see the same patterns on a larger data basis as in Figures 3.

Again, the MDv performs best, and the AM performs worst among the investigated abstract metrics. Once more, each abstract metric performs almost equivalently for different real-world use cases. Associated with the results presented in Figures 5, we show scatter plots of the data points from which the correlation coefficients are derived in Appendix A.3, see Figures A3.

4.6 Discussion

This section discusses and assesses the results obtained from our computational study.

Overall, it can be said that the MD and MDv abstract metrics show the best correlations with the utility from our real-world use cases. Further, the DM

shows intermediate correlations, while the AM shows the lowest correlations with our real-world use cases. Overall, from the perspective of a data owner, it would be best to evaluate the utility of the anonymized data with the MD_v.

However, this statement is not yet universally valid because we evaluated only a few use cases from a single dataset in the mobility domain. To improve the robustness of the conclusion drawn, further use cases from the mobility domain and beyond must be considered, see [16], [31]. In particular, these use cases should deal with different data types such as text, image, numerical, location, or trajectory-based data.

As described in Section 4.5, we found that the correlations between one abstract metric and the different real-world utility values are almost identical, independent of the use case. This leads us to the assumption that many abstract metrics tend to yield constant correlation coefficients for a wide range of different use cases from the mobility domain. In addition, it should be noted that the correlation results are related to the selected evaluation metric, i.e. whether MAE or MAPE was selected.

The next point is that abstract metrics are primarily designed for a specific anonymization technique. In order to evaluate different anonymized datasets resulting from different anonymization techniques e.g. k -anonymity or differential privacy, abstract metrics must be used, which equally evaluate anonymizations by generalization or by noise. The most abstract metrics can determine either the generalization or noise of an anonymized dataset, see in the information metrics Table 3 from publication [1]. This means that a data owner still cannot know whether the value of utility is larger with k -anonymity or differential privacy for real-world applications. The data owner only knows that the information value is higher, for example with a $k = 2$ -anonymity than a $k = 10$ -anonymity, and consequently, the data utility value for a $k = 2$ -anonymized dataset is higher for real-world applications.

5 Summary and Outlook

This section summarizes our work and proposes directions for future research.

At the beginning of this paper, we briefly introduce in Section 2 the basics of anonymization concepts. Next, we present our framework for the utility evaluation of anonymized datasets in the mobility context, see Section 3. Our framework is based on correlations between utility metrics for real-world applications and abstract metrics for anonymization techniques. This makes it possible to find a generally valid abstract metric in the mobility domain, which can be used to estimate the data utility value for a wide range of real-world applications. Data owners can use this information to create anonymized datasets with a high likelihood that these anonymized datasets

will have a high utility in real-world applications. Furthermore, we generate three real-world use cases to demonstrate the procedure and obtain use case-specific results, see Section 4. It results that the MDv performs best for these use cases of the price prediction of the New York taxi dataset. After that, our results and current advantages and disadvantages of our framework are critically discussed in Section 4.6.

For future research, we plan to implement further use cases and prediction models based on various datasets from the mobility domain to evaluate the general validity of our results. Further, testing other anonymization techniques like differential privacy and implementing related abstract metrics is a further open task. Abstract metrics for differential privacy can be, among others, the statistically-based L_p -Norm [32] or the Hellinger distance [33], see [1].

Another research task is to compare anonymized datasets resulting from different anonymization techniques, e.g. k -anonymity and differential privacy. This would allow a data owner to assess which of these anonymization techniques under which specifications provide the highest utility in real-world applications and decide whether to publish an anonymized dataset to customers in the form of k -anonymity or differential privacy. This would require an abstract metric that considers the generalization and noise simultaneously.

In addition, an abstract metric could also be designed to offer an even higher correlation to real-world utilities than the existing abstract metrics.

Since image data is also a large subset of mobility data, computer vision models could also be implemented to evaluate different anonymizations of images. In general, anonymizing image data is a big challenge, as privacy protection is difficult to guarantee because of secondary aspects of images and entails a lot of research potential.

Last, the trade-off between the data utility value and the associated security due to anonymizations is to be investigated.

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A Appendix

A.1 Anonymized datasets tables

Number:	k	Hierarchy-Level:	Pick-up Zone Size:	Drop-off Zone Size:
1	2	(1, 1, 1, 2)	500x500 meter	500x1000 meter
2	3	(1, 1, 1, 4)	500x5000 meter	500x4000 meter
3	4	(1, 2, 1, 3)	500x1000 meter	500x2000 meter
4	5	(2, 2, 2, 2)	1000x1000 meter	1000x1000 meter
5	7	(3, 1, 3, 2)	2000x500 meter	2000x1000 meter
6	8	(1, 4, 2, 2)	500x4000 meter	1000x1000 meter
7	9	(3, 3, 2, 1)	2000x2000 meter	1000x500 meter
8	10	(1, 1, 4, 3)	500x500 meter	4000x2000 meter
9	13	(3, 2, 3, 2)	2000x1000 meter	2000x1000 meter
10	15	(3, 3, 2, 2)	2000x2000 meter	1000x1000 meter
11	20	(4, 3, 1, 3)	4000x2000 meter	500x2000 meter
12	25	(4, 2, 2, 3)	4000x1000 meter	1000x2000 meter
13	30	(1, 2, 4, 4)	500x1000 meter	4000x4000 meter
14	50	(3, 3, 3, 3)	2000x2000 meter	2000x2000 meter
15	70	(1, 2, 5, 5)	500x1000 meter	8000x8000 meter
16	100	(3, 3, 4, 4)	2000x2000 meter	4000x4000 meter
17	200	(4, 2, 5, 4)	4000x1000 meter	8000x4000 meter
18	300	(4, 4, 4, 4)	4000x4000 meter	4000x4000 meter
19	700	(3, 4, 5, 5)	2000x4000 meter	8000x8000 meter
20	1000	(3, 4, 6, 5)	2000x4000 meter	16000x8000 meter

Table A1: Used anonymization properties for the February dataset 2015.

Number:	k	Hierarchy-Level:	Pick-up Zone Size:	Drop-off Zone Size:
1	2	(1, 2, 1, 2)	500x1000 meter	500x1000 meter
2	3	(1, 2, 1, 3)	500x1000 meter	500x2000 meter
3	4	(2, 2, 2, 2)	1000x1000 meter	1000x1000 meter
4	5	(3, 1, 3, 2)	2000x500 meter	2000x1000 meter
5	7	(1, 2, 3, 3)	500x1000 meter	2000x2000 meter
6	8	(3, 2, 3, 2)	2000x1000 meter	2000x1000 meter
7	9	(3, 3, 2, 2)	2000x2000 meter	1000x1000 meter
8	10	(1, 2, 4, 3)	500x1000 meter	4000x2000 meter
9	13	(4, 4, 2, 1)	4000x4000 meter	1000x500 meter
10	15	(4, 3, 1, 3)	4000x2000 meter	500x2000 meter
11	20	(2, 2, 3, 4)	1000x1000 meter	2000x4000 meter
12	25	(3, 3, 3, 3)	2000x2000 meter	2000x2000 meter
13	30	(2, 4, 2, 4)	1000x4000 meter	1000x4000 meter
14	50	(1, 2, 5, 5)	500x1000 meter	8000x8000 meter
15	70	(3, 3, 4, 4)	2000x2000 meter	4000x4000 meter
16	100	(2, 2, 5, 5)	1000x1000 meter	8000x8000 meter
17	200	(4, 4, 4, 4)	4000x4000 meter	4000x4000 meter
18	300	(3, 5, 3, 5)	2000x8000 meter	2000x8000 meter
19	700	(3, 4, 6, 5)	2000x4000 meter	16000x8000 meter
20	1000	(4, 4, 5, 5)	4000x4000 meter	8000x8000 meter

Table A2: Used anonymization properties for the October dataset 2015.

A.2 Further correlation results

(a) Evaluated with the MAE

(b) Evaluated with the MAPE

Figure A1: Correlation coefficients plots between abstract metrics and real-world utility values for February 2015.

(a) Evaluated with the MAE

(b) Evaluated with the MAPE

Figure A2: Correlation coefficients plots between abstract metrics and real-world utility values for October 2015.

A.3 Scatter plots building correlation coefficients

(a) Evaluated with the MAE

(b) Evaluated with the MAPE

Figure A3: Building of correlation coefficients between a specific abstract metric and a real-world utility from the New York taxi dataset from February, July, and October 2015.